

Career Anxiety Among Tourism Students in The New Normal: Evidence from A State University in The Philippines

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ABSTRACT: This study evaluates the level of career anxiety among tourism students in a state university in the Philippines during the new normal. Using a quantitative survey design, data were collected from 100 Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management students which was selected through stratified random sampling. Specifically, it determined whether significant differences exist when students are grouped according to sex, year level, sibling rank, and family monthly income. Data were collected using an adapted Future Career Anxiety Scale and analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-test, and one-way ANOVA at a 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that students generally experienced a normal level of career anxiety across all profile variables. Furthermore, there is no significant differences were found in career anxiety when grouped according to sex, sibling rank, and family income, while year level showed minimal variation. The results suggest that although students experience uncertainty due to external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic, their anxiety remains manageable. The study highlights the importance of institutional support, including career guidance and counseling programs, to help students navigate career uncertainties.

KEYWORDS: Career Anxiety, New Normal, Tourism Management, Tourism Students, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry is highly vulnerable to global crises, with the COVID-19 pandemic significantly affected the employment opportunities and career pathways of future tourism workforces which are our students. The pandemic caused tourism demand huge declines globally, resulting in extensive loss of employment and instability across the tourism sector (United Nations World Tourism Organization, 2021; International Labor Organization, 2020). As one of the most affected industry, tourism has created uncertainty among students preparing to enter the workforce. This uncertainty often leads to career anxiety, which is defined as the fear and emotional distress associated with future career decisions (Mahmud et al., 2021).

Tourism students who dream to be part of the tourism industry, particularly those in higher education, are among those who were the most affected due to limited job opportunities and unstable industry conditions during and after the pandemic (Aucejo et al., 2020; Zopiatis et al., 2021). The sudden change in employment market conditions has raised concerns regarding employability and career readiness.

Understanding their level of career anxiety is important in designing effective support mechanisms for students transitioning into the workforce. Previous studies suggest that factors such as income, gender, and educational level may influence anxiety levels (Cao et al., 2020; Son et al., 2020). However, limited research has examined these variables specifically in the context of tourism students adapting to the new normal.

Therefore, this study aims to determine the level of career anxiety among tourism students a state university in the Philippines. Specifically, it seeks to determine the extent of career anxiety in terms of sex, year level, sibling rank, and family monthly income, and to examine whether significant differences exist when grouped according to these factors. The findings of this study may serve as a basis for developing student support services, targeted career guidance initiatives, and institutional programs that aim to reduce anxiety and enhance career readiness among tourism students.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design. Stratified random sampling method of research was also implemented in this study. This method was used to determine the career anxiety of Tourism Management students in the new normal. In this study, the independent variable is sex, year level, sibling rank and family's monthly income while the dependent variable is tourism students' career anxiety.

The respondents of the study were the 100 selected students of the Bachelor of Science in Tourism and Management (BSTM) in a

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State University. To get the reasonable accuracy of results, they were determined through the use of Slovin's formula. The respondents were classified according to sex, year level, sibling rank, and family's monthly income. Sex pertained to whether the respondent is male or female. Year level referred to the respondent being a 1st year, 2nd year or 3rd year college student.

Sibling rank refers to the respondent's birth order whether he/she is the eldest, middle child, or the youngest among their siblings.

The research devised an online survey questionnaire to gather data. The questionnaire was adopted from Future Career Anxiety Scale (FCA) by Tsai et al. (2017). The instrument was designed to identify the students' level of career anxiety. Items are randomly arranged on the questionnaire to reduce getting a response error. The form is composed of two sections. The first part depicts the personal data of the respondents, such as name, sex, year level, sibling rank and family's monthly income. The second part contained questions that aimed to draw out responses on the career anxiety experienced by Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management Students in West Visayas State University. The respondents were asked to tick the check box on the survey questionnaire form to indicate their answer or respond on each item. A 4-point Likert scale was adopted for questions 1 to 6 (1= strongly disagree and 4= strongly agree) and a Reversed 4-Point Likert scale was adopted for questions 7 to 15 (1= strongly agree and 4= strongly disagree); a high score indicated a high anxiety level.

The gathered data was subjected to these statistical treatments such as Percentage analysis was used to find out what part of total respondents belonged to a certain category such as sex, year level, sibling rank and family's monthly income. Frequency count was used to determine the number of participants belonging to a class or category of the antecedent variables. Mean was utilized to determine the career anxiety of the tourism students. The standard deviation was used to ascertain the homogeneity and heterogeneity among the tourism students' career anxiety. The t-test for independent samples was utilized to determine whether significant differences occurred in the career anxiety among tourism students. One- way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant differences in tourism students' career anxiety categorized according to sex, age, sibling rank, year level and family's monthly income. The 0.05 alpha level was utilized as the criterion for the acceptance or rejection of the null hypothesis.

CONCLUSION

The findings revealed that tourism students experienced a normal level of career anxiety across all categories, including sex, year level, sibling rank, and family income. Mean scores ranged from 2.19 to 2.41, indicating moderate emotional stability despite uncertainties. In terms of differences, statistical analysis showed that there was no significant difference in career anxiety when grouped according to sex ($p = .533$). In addition, there is no significant differences were observed in sibling rank and family income. Year level showed slight variation but remained within the normal anxiety range.

These findings suggest that career anxiety is a shared experience among tourism students regardless of demographic background. This may be attributed to the widespread impact of the pandemic on the tourism industry, which created a generalized sense of uncertainty among future professionals. The study concludes that tourism students experience a normal level of career anxiety despite the challenges brought by the new normal. Moreover, demographic factors such as sex, year level, sibling rank, and family income do not significantly influence anxiety levels.

This indicates that career anxiety among students is more likely influenced by external factors such as industry instability rather than personal characteristics.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, it is recommended that higher education institutions should strengthen their career guidance programs and support services to help tourism students effectively manage their career anxiety. In addition, the institutions should proactively reach out to all student populations, identify students at risk of future career anxiety, and provide accessible career counselling and employment consultation services. Gaining an understanding of students' career decision-making is important for both universities and their students. This may involve helping students to make appropriate career decisions based on understanding the career decision-making process or to assist them to recognize how the industry can help them achieve their career choices.

Universities should also develop a curriculum that prepares students for their future careers. Universities can arrange trainings, career counselling, and job fairs to provide job opportunities for students.

Further research using a larger sample from other courses is highly recommended. Further research is proposed for the inclusion of successful coping strategies used by the students during testing times such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Research should also be channeled toward career counseling, trainings and assessment methods in the "new normal" space, which can have the dual benefit of maximizing learning outcomes and minimizing career anxiety among students. Further research on counseling practices based on reducing career anxiety for students in the career decision-making process is also recommended.

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